

MORAL AND LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF INFORMATION
SECURITY IN UZBEKISTAN

Inaxamova Nodiraxon Muhammad Ibrohim qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

nodirainaxamova@gmail.com

Abstract: In this article, we will talk about the loss and alteration of information about what is information security it is said that information is protected on any carriers from accidental and intentional effects of directed natural or artificial nature.

Key words: information security, information resources, constitution, information reserve, technologies, information systems.

Loss and alteration of data in the name of information security it is said that information is protected on any carriers from accidental and intentional effects of directed natural or artificial nature. It is known from history that the previous threat was only the theft or copying of confidential messages and documents, while the current threat is the collection of computer data, electronic data, electronic arrays without asking the owner's permission. is to use. "In addition to these, the desire to get material benefits from these actions has also developed." Information protection must be organized in such processes.

"Information protection" management and production activities ensuring information security and the integrity of the organization's information reserves, robust, ensuring reliability, ease of use and privacy to the regulated dynamic technological process" to the owner of the information, illegal that wants to harm its user and another person any documented, i.e., identification from the transaction the information recorded on the tangible object should be protected if the details of the provider are provided.

The objectives of information protection are as follows is:

- prevention of unauthorized leakage, theft, loss, alteration, falsification of information;
- prevention of danger to personal, society, state security;
- prevention of unauthorized actions to destroy, change, falsify, copy, suppress information;
- ensuring the legal order in the amount of documented information, preventing any attempts of illegal interference with the information reserve and information system;
- protection of the constitutional rights of citizens who protect personal privacy and confidentiality of personal information available in the information system;

- to keep the state secret, the confidentiality of documented information according to law;
- ensuring the rights of subjects in the creation, development and use of information systems, technologies and the tools that provide them.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the main source of norms regulating relations in the field of information in our country. The most important and forward-looking plans and goals of the life of the state and society are defined in the basic law. In particular, information and relations related to it are defined in the chapter "Personal rights and freedoms" of our basic law. All the rest is in the field of information Laws and regulations regulating relations are our basic law It was adopted on the basis of our Constitution and to strengthen the norms established in it. We can see that in many norms of our constitution, which is a regulatory legal document that primarily regulates the most important aspects of the state and society, information security is regulated in a legal way.

According to this norm, the representatives of the fields and sectors that work organically with information in our country are directly responsible for the reliability and validity of the information they collect and distribute, as well as for compliance with the information and the requirements and standards set for it. That is, mass media are directly responsible for the accuracy and truthfulness of the transmitted information. In addition, the following norms in Articles 27 and 29 of our constitution are the main legal norms that serve to directly ensure information security: may not reveal the secret of correspondence and telephone conversations", this constitutional norm also strengthens the norm of ensuring the security of information and protecting the security of citizens in the field of information.

It is determined that the state regulation of the information sector will be carried out by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the body it has specially authorized. According to this law, information resources containing information on state secrets and confidential information or information whose free use is restricted by the owners of information resources are included in information resources with restricted access, and the owners and owners of information resources can freely use them all. it is necessary to ensure the free use of possible information resources by legal entities and individuals on the basis of equal rights.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "Uzbekistan" 2020. Page 22
2. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "Uzbekistan" 2020. Page 12
3. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Keeping State Secrets". Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, - 1993. - №5.
4. Karimov I. A. The concept of further deepening of democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country. - T., 2010.
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Personal Information". National database of legal documents, - 03.077.2019. - #3363.
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Information". Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2004. - #36. - 19-20 m.
7. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information". Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. -2003. - #1. - 2nd m.
8. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/o-zbekiston-respublikasida-axborot-xavfsizligini-ta-minlovchi-huquqiy-hujjatlar-va-ularning-tahlili>